

Kinetic studies of oxidation of nickel(II) macrocyclic complexes by peroxydisulphate ion in aqueous media

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Abstract : The macrocyclic complexes of the transition metals in unusual degree of oxidation have been studied. Nickel(II) tetraazamacrocycles bearing pendant alkyl groups were synthesized and the kinetic studies of the oxidation of nickel(II) macrocycles by the peroxydisulphate anion ($S_2O_8^{2-}$) have been studied in aqueous media. The rate increases with increase of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ concentration. The effect of pH on reaction rate has also been studied. Increase in the rate of reaction occurs along with the increase in pH.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} , kinetics, oxidation, peroxydisulphate ion.

Introduction

Redox properties play an important role for the chemical behaviour of transition metal complexes. It is noteworthy that for the natural and synthetic complexes involving macrocyclic ligands and their derivatives which are known to mimic the properties and reactivity very close to those of the cyclam analogue¹. Almost all macrocyclic complexes of nickel investigated so far display the typical macrocyclic inertness towards demetallation by strong acids².

Most of the Ni^{II} macrocyclic complexes have been isolated as perchlorate salt in the reaction solution. These are water soluble and show kinetic stability³⁻⁵. There are evidences that complexes of the transition metals represent as intermediate in catalytic, electrocatalytic and biological redox processes^{6,7}. There have been many kinetic studies of oxidations by the peroxydisulphate anion ($S_2O_8^{2-}$). Although $S_2O_8^{2-}$ is a very strong two electron oxidant, its redox reactions are usually slow⁸⁻¹⁰.

The kinetics of redox processes with the participation of different nickel complexes have so far not been studied sufficiently. The literature shows that the kinetics of oxidation of some tetraazamacrocyclic complexes of nickel(II) with radicals are generated in pulse radiolysis or photolysis. The oxidation reactions are proceeded practically at diffusion controlled rates and they differ little for different complexes^{11,12}.

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of Ni^{II} tetraazamacrocycles by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ anion in aqueous and binary aqueous mixtures have already been reported^{13,14}. The modification in the framework of macrocycles such as variation of ring size, introduction of alkyl substituents, unsaturation etc. has shown to affect the redox properties of macrocycles. In this present paper, the kinetics of oxidation of two Ni^{II} tetraazamacrocycles $[Ni^{II}A]^{2+}$ and $[Ni^{II}B]^{2+}$ have been taken into account as function of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and pH studies.

Experimental

Potassium peroxydisulphate (CDH) AnalaR grade was used as such. Lithium perchlorate was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. All other reagents and solvents were of AnalaR grade and were used without further purification. All solutions were made in doubly distilled water.

The Ni^{II} macrocycle (A) and Ni^{II} macrocycle (B) perchlorate complexes were prepared by a literature procedure¹⁵⁻¹⁸ and their characterization was carried out by IR, UV-Vis and CHN analysis.

Preparation of macrocyclic complexes (General procedure) :

Both complexes were synthesized by the template method by condensation of ethylenediamine and acetone/acetyl acetone in the presence of salt (chloride). To a methanolic solvent (≈ 50 ml), ethylenediamine, and ace-

tone/acetyl acetone followed by metal salt in the ratio 2 : 2 : 1 were added in round bottom flask. The mixture was shaken well and refluxed for 6–8 h. The change in colour was appeared. 4–5 drops of perchloric acid were also added at the end of the reaction. The round bottom flask was kept aside for its cooling. The filtration and washing were carried out by methanol and dried in vacuum. The coloured complexes were obtained and taken for further studies.

(A) 1,4,8,11-Tetraaza-5,7,12,14-tetramethyltetradeca-4,11-diene Ni^{II} macrocyclic complex.

(B) 1,4,8,11-Tetraaza-5,7,7,12,14,14-hexamethyltetradeca-4,11-diene Ni^{II} macrocyclic complex.

Kinetics :

All kinetic experiments were carried out in aqueous media using doubly distilled water. Kinetic studies were performed under pseudo-first order conditions using an excess of peroxydisulphate. Concentrations of the Ni^{II} macrocyclic complexes used in this experiment were $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The absorbance changes were measured using a spectrophotometer (Systronics UV-Vis spectrophotometer 117). Before mixing, the solutions of the reactants were thermostated at the given temperature for 15 min. Dilute perchloric acid was added for stabilization of Ni^{II} complexes in acidic media, as well as in the presence of coordinating ligands, which are known from literature studies^{19,20}. Ionic strength was maintained at 0.5 mol dm^{-3} for all kinetic runs, using lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄). Absorbance measurements for kinetics were made at 410 nm and 572 nm wavelength (Table 1). The kinetic study was kept limited only to the period in which λ_{max} of the reaction mixture did not change and no precipitation took place during the study of any kinetic run.

Table 1. λ_{max} and elemental analysis of macrocyclic complexes A and B

Macrocyclic complex	λ_{max} (nm)	Calcd. (Found) %			
		C	H	N	M
Complex A	410	33.09	5.12	11.03	11.56
		(32.90)	(5.02)	(10.98)	(11.00)
Complex B	572	35.84	5.6	10.45	10.95
		(35.00)	(5.4)	(10.20)	(10.01)

Results and discussion

The synthesized complexes were crystalline solids and

non hygroscopic. The IR spectral data indicates some important assignments (Table 2). The complexes A and B exhibit a C=N absorption at 1603 cm^{-1} and 1601 cm^{-1} respectively which together with the absence of C=O

Table 2. IR spectral data of macrocyclic complexes A and B (cm⁻¹)

Macrocyclic complex	C=N	NH	$\text{>C(CH}_3)_2$	ClO ₄
Complex A	1603	3331	-	1048
Complex B	1601	3320	1380	1076

absorption around 1700 cm^{-1} . It shows that amino group of ethylenediamine was condensed with the carbonyl group of acetylacetone/acetone to give a cyclic structure. In the complexes, N-H bands were observed at 3331 cm^{-1} and 3320 cm^{-1} . In Ni macrocyclic complex B, band at 1380 cm^{-1} shows the presence of two methyl groups at same carbon. Analytical data (Table 1) and IR spectroscopic data enable us to predict the possible structure of the synthesized complexes (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

In kinetic studies using UV-Vis spectral changes, a decrease in the absorbance was observed followed by a slower decrease. For both complexes under investigations, kinetic runs were made at different concentrations of one reactant, keeping the concentration of others constant^{21,22}. The initial rate method was used to decide the kinetic behaviour of these reactions. Initial rates $(dA/dt)_5$ were evaluated after 5 min from the start of the reaction by using plate mirror method²³ from the plot of absorbance (A) vs time (t). The straight line plots plotted between initial rates in terms of $(dA/dt)_5$ vs concentration confirms the first order kinetics (Fig. 3).

The most commonly used method for first order rate constant evaluation is Guggenheim method. At time t with

Fig. 2. UV-Visible spectral changes during the oxidation of Ni^{II} complex A by peroxydisulphate. Changes were taken at 1 min intervals.

Fig. 3. Effect of S₂O₈²⁻ on the rate of oxidation of Ni^{II} complex A and B.

equal intervals are recorded. For the same reaction, next series of readings $A_{(t+dt)}$ is also completed where dt is a constant time increment. A plot between $\log [A_t - A_{(t+dt)}]$ vs time gives a slope equal to $-k_1/2.303$. This slope yields a first order rate constant k_1 ²⁴.

Table 3 lists first order rate constant for the oxidation of the nickel(II) macrocycles by [S₂O₈²⁻] in aqueous solution as a function of oxidant. It indicates k_1 increases by increasing S₂O₈²⁻ concentration.

In this experiment, pH was varied by taking acetate buffer and phosphate buffer. The summarized Table 4

Table 3. First order rate constants for the oxidation of Ni^{II} macrocyclic complexes as a function of [S₂O₈²⁻] in aqueous media

Temp = 30 ± 1 °C, μ = 0.5 mol dm⁻³

Ni complex (A) = 5 × 10 ⁻³ (mol dm ⁻³)			Ni complex (B) = 5 × 10 ⁻³ (mol dm ⁻³)		
[S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	Rate × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)	[S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	Rate × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)
0.025	0.8	2.30	0.025	0.6	2.45
0.05	1.6	2.76	0.05	1.0	2.91
0.075	2.4	3.68	0.075	1.4	3.83
0.1	3.2	4.29	0.1	2	4.45
0.125	4	4.91	0.125	2.4	5.22
0.150	4.8	5.83	0.150	3.0	6.14

shows that as the pH of the solution increases, the reaction rate also goes on increasing (as shown in Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on the rate of oxidation of Ni^{II} complex A and B.

Pseudo-first order kinetics is observed for the appearance of Ni^{III} product in aqueous media. If SO₄⁻ radicals involved in the rate determining step during the reaction, deviation from first order behaviour in the oxidation of peroxydisulphate would have occurred^{25,26}.

The addition of a radical scavenger, allyl acetate, caused no change in rates. This suggests that the rate determining step does not involve the SO₄⁻ species. The nickel(II) macrocyclic complexes oxidized smoothly to the tervalent state. Fig. 2 shows the time dependence of the UV/Visible spectrum of Ni macrocycle A with peroxydisulphate. It shows an intense absorption at 390 nm.

Table 4. First order rate constant for the oxidation of Ni^{II} macrocyclic complexes under various pH conditions

Temp = 30 ± 1 °C, μ = 0.5 mol dm⁻³

Ni complex (A) = 5 × 10 ⁻³ (mol dm ⁻³) [S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻] = 5 × 10 ⁻² mol dm ⁻³			Ni complex (B) = 5 × 10 ⁻³ (mol dm ⁻³) [S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻] = 5 × 10 ⁻² mol dm ⁻³		
pH	Rate × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)	pH	Rate × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)
2.4	1.0	1.84	2.4	0.8	2.14
2.8	1.2	2.14	2.8	1.0	2.61
3.2	1.4	2.76	3.2	1.2	2.91
3.6	1.6	3.07	3.6	1.4	3.37
4.0	1.8	3.53	4.0	1.8	3.68
4.4	2.0	3.76	4.4	2.2	3.99
5.0	2.4	4.14	5.0	2.8	4.45
5.6	2.8	4.60	5.6	3.2	4.75
6.0	3.0	4.83	6.0	3.4	5.06
7.0	3.2	5.37	7.0	3.6	5.52

The overall reaction may be described as,

A simplified mechanism (ignoring for the moment, interchange between possible inner sphere solvent at the Ni^{II} complex and peroxydisulphate) may be described schematically as^{27,28},

The rate law derived from this scheme is

$$\text{Rate} = 2k_3K_{\text{ip}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \frac{[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{A}]_{\text{tot}}}{(1 + K_{\text{ip}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}])} \quad (5)$$

In the present system, the term (1 + K_{ip} [S₂O₈²⁻]) approximates to unity.

This suggests that the ion-pairing constant is small and the approximation,

$$1 + K_{\text{ip}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] = 1$$

Hence the rate law is simplified to

$$\text{Rate} = k_1[\text{NiA}^{2+}]$$

$$\text{Rate} = 2k_3K_{\text{ip}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}][\text{NiA}^{2+}]$$

An important feature of Ni^{II} macrocycles is the coexistence in solution of the high spin and low spin form, according to the interconversion equilibrium^{29,30}.

where A is the macrocycle and S solvent molecule displaying donor properties. A visible colour change from green to yellow observed after the addition of oxidant. Firstly absorbance decreases because high spin form reacts with the oxidant. After this, the high spin form is transformed into the more stable low spin form results slower decrease in the absorbance³¹.

Further, introduction of alkyl substituents results stronger ligand field towards the coordinated Ni^{II} ion. Hence Ni complex B provides a considerably stronger ligand field for a coordinated metal ion in comparison to Ni complex A. Therefore k₁ values for Ni complex B are higher compared to that of Ni complex A. It has been concluded from these studies that these macrocyclic complexes are behaving similarly accordingly to the Ni^{II} macrocycles different from these complexes.

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